

"*Dragen van mondkapjes niet nodig is*" "*mondkapjes zijn verplicht*"
How the Netherlands dealt with the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic

Iris Baas, Marc Esteve Del Valle, Tommaso Caselli

University of Groningen

`i.m.baas@rug.nl`

The COVID-19 pandemic is the first worldwide crisis occurring at a time when social media and the Internet have become prominent outlets of information production and consumption. This is one of the reasons why the General Secretary of U.N. has warned against the dangers of the accompanying *infodemic*, i.e., "a tsunami of hate, xenophobia, scapegoating and scare-mongering."¹ As in any other crises and disasters, "good communication saves lives".² This paper presents an investigation on the use of Twitter during the first wave of the COVID-19 in the Netherlands by three authoritative groups, namely politicians, government institutions, and news media. The Netherlands is an interesting case study as the Dutch crisis approach towards COVID-19 has been different from most other European countries, especially in terms of strictness of the measures and infrastructure of testing and vaccination. At the time of the first wave of the pandemic, the Netherlands was also facing general elections. This might have influenced the choices for communication strategies, as public approval was important to political parties and individual politicians, especially for those with an authoritative role in the management of the pandemic.

Social media allows two-way communication enabling interaction between different groups of people with different societal roles during a crisis, creating an interesting dynamic in terms of crisis communication. Previous work in communication crisis and in crisis informatics (Palen and Liu, 2007; Palen et al., 2009; Olteanu et al., 2015; Imran et al., 2015) has shown the effectiveness of social media as tools for enhancing situational awareness of crisis, both for citizens and for response organizations (e.g., fire brigades, police, municipal services, the Red Cross, or other governmental organizations). However, it has been suggested that institutions and response organizations struggle in an effective use of social media for crisis communication strategies (Acar and Muraki, 2011; Hughes and Palen, 2012; Jin et al., 2014; van der Meer and Verhoeven, 2013). We approach this investigation with care, being aware of the many meanings associated with "crisis" and their nature (i.e., human-caused vs. natural) that social science

¹A. Guterres, General Secretary of the U.N.,
<https://www.un.org/en/coronavirus/good-communication-saves-lives>

² *Ibid.*

research has identified (Quarantelli, 2005; Perry, 2018) and the risks of flattening this richness with the communication medium (Palen and Hughes, 2018). Although the very nature of a crisis requires different types of information and ways to obtain them, failure from emergency managers to effectively provide social media communication around a crisis may trigger citizens to obtain information elsewhere (Palen and Hughes, 2018). This may have nefarious effects in a crisis such as the one caused by COVID-19, increasing the dangers of exposure to misinformation and malevolent agents.

This work adopts a mixed method approach, where quantitative observations based on a large collection of Twitter data are further refined by applying a qualitative analysis grounded on Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA; Catalano and Waugh, 2020; Van Dijk, 2014; Fairclough 2013) The quantitative analysis has been conducted using *Voyant*.³ In particular, for each of the targeted groups, we have extracted different types of data ranging from word-trees to keywords, that have been used in combination with the *Trends* graph. The keyword selection allowed for a simple analysis of which words were most frequent across each subset of tweets. The data extracted from *Voyant* are the basis for the qualitative analysis of the *discourse* and themes in each group (and relevant subgroups).

We have used the `40twene_nl` corpus (Caselli and Basile, 2020),⁴ a collection of more than 4 million tweets in Dutch about COVID-19 from February to December 2020. We have focused our analysis on 4.1 million tweets between March and September 2020, covering the first wave of COVID-19 in the Netherlands. The initial 4.1 million messages were filtered and gathered in three categories; (1) news media, (2) politicians and (3) government institutions. These categories represent important authoritative actors in communicating crises in The Netherlands. We limited the news outlet to the top four newspapers (*De Telegraaf*, *Algemeen Dagblad*, *NRC*, and *Volkscrant*) and top three broadcast companies (*NOS*, *Één vandaag*, and *NPO1*). For the politicians, all party leaders and ‘*fractie voorzitters*’ [parliamentary leaders] were selected. We selected both members of the ruling coalition parties and opposition. Finally, we selected only governmental organizations that play an active role in dealing with the COVID pandemic. The list comprises the RIVM (National Institute for Public Health and Environment), The Ministry of the Interior and Kingdom Relations (BZK), The Ministry of Health, the Rijksoverheid, the GGD and GHOR (public health services), and NCTV (National Coordinator of Terrorism and Security). The Twitter account of the Prime Minister was included in this latter category rather than in the ‘politicians’. The final outcome resulted in a total of 7,798 messages,

³ <https://voyant-tools.org>

⁴ https://osf.io/pfnur/?view_only=5cc01c6cad8441eb47659459fd5db10

distributed as follows: 6,364 for the news media, 622 for the politicians, and 812 for the government institutions.

The findings of this research reveal that although all three categories used Twitter to communicate the COVID-19 crisis, there was a lack of a coherent and consistent strategy within but also between categories. In all three categories, Twitter was mainly used for one-way communication and to redirect users elsewhere, rather than using the tool as a method to engage with the public.

The three actors had different purposes for using the platform, which sometimes led to preposterous results. News media mainly contributed to situational awareness about COVID-19 in the Netherlands as well as in other European countries. This continuous "update-and-compare" activity contributed to an information overflow that sometimes challenged the discourses the government tried to enforce in order to create a coherent crisis response. A peculiar use of Twitter by news outlets was to redirect readers to the paywalled website of the news outlet themselves. The main goal of the tweets by this actor was to *activate and intrigue* people, which resulted in sometimes even *sensationalistic messages*.

Politicians have mostly used Twitter to communicate their standpoints regarding the pandemic. This is likely related to the fact that, at the time, there were upcoming general elections in The Netherlands. Twitter was also used by politicians to express critique on certain parts of the crisis response. The right wing politicians seemed to be especially critical in terms of the restriction of freedoms due to COVID-19 measures.

While government institutions were active on Twitter, especially in the early stage of the pandemic, a clear narrative or communication strategy was lacking. This resulted in weak and sometimes even contradictory information flows. This issue was recognised by the government and prompted the launch of the 'alleen samen' [only together] campaign. Only at the end of April 2020,⁵ the government published the first communication strategy booklet ('handreiking'). While indications of use of language that can help to "pass the message through" is given, a clear approach on how to use social media is lacking (e.g., they are only mentioned as potential channels but there is no indication of *how* to use them).

One of the biggest flaws in the crisis communication strategies that are currently applied on social media among the three actors is the lack of dialogical purposes. While this two-way communication could be beneficial, the platform is still mostly used in a one-way communication setting to redirect users (either paid articles or external web pages where information is given) .

⁵<https://www.communicatierijk.nl/documenten/publicaties/2020/04/24/handreiking-communicatieaanpak-coronabestrijding>

Only the politicians have actually used the platform as a tool for dialogue, mainly with their supporters rather than with the whole population.

The analysis of our data makes evident that all three actors have competing goals for using Twitter rather than solely to achieve mitigation of the crisis. Therefore, at times, discourses in one group of actors conflict with those of another group, which might affect the effectiveness of the crisis management negatively. For example, while the government was propagating PCR-testing and social distancing, within the politicians category the opposition parties were publicly questioning the effectiveness of the tests. Furthermore, some of the coalition parties were pointing out the negative effects (economical and mental) of the restriction measures for small business owners and marginalized groups. Different ideas were propagated by authoritative figures simultaneously, which may have led to confusion for the general public and negatively affected the effectiveness of the crisis management. While different actors can use a tool such as Twitter freely and democratically to express themselves, it is important to be aware of the influence and interactions among these actors and the weight that each voice has on social media platforms, so that the crisis response can be adapted.

Further research focusing on how Twitter can be used for dialogical methods of crisis communication and management is recommended. More generally, there is a need to gain a better understanding of how contemporary communication tools such as Social Media are used in times of a crisis. While the responsibility to address this might lie within academia, this knowledge also needs to be communicated to those who need to apply it: news media, politicians, and government institutions.

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